

2. Ur, Penny. A Course in Language Teaching: Practice and Theory. — Speaking va pronunciation komponentlari, fluency va accuracy concepts are explaine

HOW TO IMPROVE MEMORIZING THE WORDS

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Abstract: This article discusses effective methods for memorizing vocabulary in a simple and practical way. It explains how techniques such as spaced repetition, flashcards, active recall and using words in sentences can significantly improve long-term memory. The article also highlights the importance of thematic grouping, visual learning, and using new words regularly in daily communication. By applying these strategies, learners can make vocabulary learning easier, faster, and more enjoyable.

Key words: Long-term memory, word retention, learner engagement, vocabulary, recall

Introduction: Memorizing words plays a key role in learning any language because vocabulary is the foundation of communication. The more words a learner knows, the more confidently they can express ideas, understand reading texts, follow conversations, and write clearly. A strong vocabulary also improves pronunciation and helps students think directly in the target language instead of translating from their mother tongue. When learners have a wide range of words in their memory, they can understand new topics faster and develop better speaking and listening skills. Why We Should Memorize: Memorizing vocabulary is necessary. Knowing enough words helps learners understand

others, speak more fluently, and perform well in language tasks. Good vocabulary makes the whole learning process easier and more effective. But some learners have been facing challenges. For example: Forgetting words quickly: Without consistent review, new vocabulary disappears from memory. Lack of context: Memorizing lists without understanding usage makes learning difficult. Low motivation: Repeating the same words can feel boring or stressful. Overloading information: Trying to learn too many words at once leads to confusion. Limited exposure: If learners don't use words in speaking or writing, they are forgotten. These challenges slow down vocabulary development and reduce confidence in language learners. However, there are some methods to improve memorizing the words

1. Use Spaced Repetition (2357) method
Hermann Ebbinghaus was the German psychologist who discovered the forgetting curve and consequently invented Spaced Repetition method for dealing with it. Use the 2357 method in reverse to plan revision sessions ahead of an exam:
 1. Start from the date of exam and plan a revision session the day before
 2. Two days before last session plan another
 3. Count five days back and plan a session there
 4. Then count seven days back and plan first study session(<https://www.iangibbs.me/post/famous-learning-technique-1-the-ebbinghaus-method>)
2. Learn with Flashcards
Flashcards are a powerful technique to enhance long term memory of concepts as this technique utilizes a combination of the 6 Effective Learning Strategies. At a minimum, creating and using flashcards allows you to practice retrieving/recalling information. Beyond this, can incorporate visuals, concrete examples, and practice spacing memorization. Flashcards are also useful for chunking information into smaller pieces to help lessen the demand on information processing and long-term memory. (<https://www.utoronto.ca/learningstrategies/flashcards>)
3. Use the Words in Sentences
Word usage is important when writing or speaking because word usage is what helps to clearly articulate points with meanings and forms that are appropriate for the context and structure of a sentence. Understanding words and

how to use them will greatly improve ability to be an effective writer. Example: “Exhausted — I was exhausted after the long exam.” (<https://www.mometrix.com/academy/word-usage/>)

4. Group Words by Theme Learning vocabulary by grouping words into themes has several benefits, including: Improved retention: Grouping words by theme helps to create meaningful connections in the brain, which can aid in retention and recall of the words. Enhanced understanding: When words are grouped by theme, it can provide a clearer understanding of how they relate to each other and to the broader context in which they are used. Efficient learning: Grouping words by theme can be an efficient way to learn and remember new words, as it allows learners to focus on related words at the same time, rather than trying to memorize them individually. (<https://digitalblackboard.io/vocab/theme/>)

Example themes: School: notebook, assignment, chalk, classroom Travel: passport, luggage, destination, ticket

5. Use Visuals and Pictures Visual information plays an important role in education. It is more appealing to students than hearing or reading plain text. According to an education consultant, people use short-term memory to process words. This means they cannot retain too much information. Images, however, go straight to the long-term memory where they permanently stay. Also, students can retain between 10 and 20 percent of spoken or written information. In comparison, they can retain around 65 percent of visual information. (<https://www.groveeyecare.com/blog/why-visual-learning-is-important-in-school.html>)

6. Practice Active Recall Active recall is a learning method where people continuously test by pulling information out of memory instead of just passively reading notes. Studies have shown (Rawson & Dunlosky, 2011; Roediger & Butler, 2011; Roediger, Putnam, & Smith, 2011) it strengthens memory and helps move information into your long term memory, making it one of the best methods for revision and studying. Flashcards are a great way to use active recall as testing with a prompt or question and strengthening the connections in brain. (<https://www.bcu.ac.uk/exams-and->

revision/best-ways-to-revise/active-recall) 7. Make Vocabulary Learning Fun It is important to recognise that young learners are still developing their cognitive ability in their own language. This impacts ability to comprehend, process and produce target language. Focus on useful words and strategies to help learners figure out meanings on their own. What exactly is a useful word? Well, primarily it is vocabulary which learners will be able to use and is relevant to their lives, as well as high frequency words which they will encounter on a regular basis. (<https://www.cambridge.org/elt/blog/2021/05/20/5-fun-ideas-make-vocabulary-jump-out-page-for-young-learners/>) Word games (e.g., Wordle, crossword puzzles) Vocabulary apps and sites (Kahoot it) Conclusion Memorizing vocabulary becomes much easier when you use smart strategies instead of trying to force words into your memory. By using spaced repetition, making sentences, visualizing words, practicing regular review, and staying consistent, you will see fast improvement. With the right methods, building your vocabulary can be both simple and enjoyable.

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